

Einstein or Bohr? 8-Theory

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Abstract:

The following is an analysis of the claims made by two of the leading scientists of the past century, Albert Einstein, which is the father of the 8T and the framework of the 8T, revolving around varying curvature. Einstein believed in determinism and full power of prediction, and could not accept the framework of QM. Bohr on the other hand, represented the ideas and the new framework (back then) of QM. Now that we have a complete theory, supported by the coupling constant series on GR framework, i.e. a Lorenz manifold, we can settle the debate and reach an interesting additional insights to whether god is playing with dices or not.

Introduction

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (0)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (2)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \bigoplus (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \bigoplus (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (2.1)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + 5 \quad (2.31)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (2.32)$$

$$e \searrow \rightarrow (\gamma) \rightarrow e \nearrow \quad (2.33)$$

$$(+3) \rightarrow (\gamma) \rightarrow (+3) \quad (2.34)$$

$$(+3) \rightarrow (+5) \rightarrow (+3) \quad (2.35)$$

$$(+3) + N_V = (+3) + 5 = 8$$

$$8 = \text{even} \rightarrow 0$$

Up to this point, everything was covered in previous paper. Now, analysis of the Einstein Bohr debate.8T vividly indicate that both Einstein and Bohr was right. Einstein was right, the magnitudes of the forces are predictable and reasonable, those magnitudes were not chosen randomly. We can explain why the photon is propagating and why the probability is what it is. In that sense, the 8T is deterministic. However, Bohr was right as well, as no data is available regarding the time or direction of propagation, it is completely random and that is the way it is in this framework, no physical data is attainable at all. God is not playing the dices, he is playing a Russian roulette, and each number of the roulette is a prime number.

Notice that the dices comment has a certain amount of irony in it, the odds on the dices, are associated with the strong, the weak and the electric, i.e. one, three and five. However, Back to our analysis, despite both great minds were right, the arguments made by Bohr seem to be closer to complete accuracy, there is very little which can be predicted, nature is random and chaotic, and the only thing we can say, is that arbitrary variations of the manifold vanish into matter, and each time a prime amount of variation (or one) appear, boson field will be propagated. That is it. It is that simple. Any question regarding position, momenta, direction or time is not possible. Einstein would not find such a reasoning beautiful, but it is beautiful. Forgive one for presenting his views, but from such a simple laws, outstanding beauty may arise, look at the complexity and beauty of the world, the variety and majesty of life. Just from the interplay between net variations, primes or one, and total variations, evens. Amazing.

References

[1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)